

Original Research

Georgia's Economic Liberalization (1991–2020): The Complementary Roles of the European Union and China in Trade, Reform, and Market Transformation

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19702241>**Publisher's Note:** NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations. **Copyright:** ©2025 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)**Abstract**

This article studies the process of economic liberalization in Georgia from 1991 to 2020 and focuses on the roles of the European Union (EU) and the People's Republic of China (PRC). The subject is important because Georgia's economic transformation is usually discussed through one external actor only, while the combined effect of the EU and China is less examined. Methods: The study uses a mixed-methods approach and combines documentary analysis, comparative analysis, and quantitative review of macroeconomic indicators. The research is based on the Dual Axis Model, which explains Georgia's liberalization through two parallel dimensions: institutional integration promoted by the EU and market integration supported by China. Data were taken from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, GeoStat, PMCG, and official documents of the European Union and the Government of Georgia. Results: The findings show that the EU had its strongest influence in institutional modernization, legal approximation, governance reform, and improvement of the business climate. China's role became stronger after 2013, especially through the Belt and Road Initiative and the China–Georgia Free Trade Agreement signed in 2017, which supported trade growth, export diversification, and connectivity. Georgia was ranked 7th in the World Bank Doing Business index in 2019, while trade turnover with China doubled between 2013 and 2020. Conclusions: The article concludes that the roles of the EU and China in Georgia were mainly complementary rather than competitive. The EU strengthened the regulatory and institutional basis of the economy, while China widened trade opportunities and market linkages. This dual pattern may offer useful lessons for other small post-Soviet economies seeking sustainable integration into the global economy.

Keywords: economic liberalization; Georgia; European Union; China; post-Soviet transformation; market integration**Introduction**

Georgia's economic transition after the collapse of the Soviet Union is an important case in the post-Soviet region. After independence in 1991, the country faced serious economic crisis conditions, hyperinflation, political instability, weak institutions, and energy shortage. In such conditions, liberalization became necessary not only for economic recovery but also for state survival and international integration. From the 1990s, Georgia tried to build a market-oriented economy and connect itself with international trade and global institutions. This process was influenced by internal reforms and external actors. Among them, the European Union and China became especially important. However,

their influence was different in form, mechanism, and timing. The European Union mainly contributed to institutional reform, legal harmonization, and regulatory modernization. Through the European Neighborhood Policy, the Eastern Partnership, the Association Agreement, and the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area, the EU supported Georgia's administrative and economic reforms. This support helped create a more transparent and predictable business environment. China's role became stronger after 2013, when the Belt and Road Initiative increased Georgia's importance as a transit and connectivity corridor. Later, the China-Georgia Free Trade Agreement, signed in 2017, created new opportunities for trade growth and export diversification. China's influence was more visible in market expansion, infrastructure cooperation, and economic connectivity. Much of the literature examines Georgia's transformation either from the side of European integration or from the side of China's economic engagement. Fewer studies examine both actors in one analytical framework. This article addresses that gap by studying how the EU and China affected Georgia's economic liberalization between 1991 and 2020. It argues that the EU and China played different but mostly complementary roles in Georgia's liberalization.

Materials and Methods

This study is based on the Dual Axis Model. This model explains Georgia's economic liberalization through two parallel dimensions. The first dimension is institutional liberalization, mainly associated with the European Union. The second dimension is market liberalization, mainly associated with China. The model helps explain how two distinct external actors influenced a single reform process through distinct mechanisms. The first axis is linked with liberal institutionalist thinking. In this understanding, the EU promotes change through rules, legal norms, regulatory approximation, and administrative standards. In Georgia, this was visible in policy reforms connected to the European Neighborhood Policy, the Eastern Partnership, the Association Agreement, and the DCFTA. These mechanisms supported institutional stabilization and regulatory modernization. The second axis is linked with the idea of connectivity and global interdependence. China's engagement was more focused on trade, logistics, infrastructure, transit routes, and investment. This role increased after the launch of the Belt and Road Initiative in 2013. For Georgia, such engagement was important because the country needed access to wider markets and more diversified economic partnerships. The article uses mixed methods. The qualitative part includes documentary analysis, literature review, and comparative reading of official agreements and policy documents. The quantitative part includes a review of macroeconomic indicators such as GDP growth, trade turnover, exports, foreign direct investment, and international business rankings. The study uses secondary data from the World Bank, International Monetary Fund, GeoStat, PMCG, official EU documents, and official Georgian sources. The period 1991-2020 was selected because it covers the full arc of Georgia's post-Soviet transition and the development of both EU and China engagement in the country.

Results and Discussions

Georgia's economic liberalization developed in several stages after independence in 1991. In the first stage, the country faced severe economic collapse, inflation, institutional weakness, and political instability. Basic reforms such as privatization, fiscal stabilization, and trade opening were introduced with support from international financial institutions. However, these early reforms were not enough to create a strong institutional foundation, and Georgia remained economically fragile during the 1990s. The role of the European Union became more important in the 2000s. Through the European Neighborhood Policy, the Eastern Partnership, the Association Agreement, and the Deep and Comprehensive Free Trade Area, the EU supported legal harmonization, administrative reform, and improvement of regulatory standards. This helped Georgia strengthen market governance and improve the business climate. The country's ranking in the World Bank Doing Business index reached 7th place in 2019, showing important progress in institutional modernization. China's role became stronger after 2013 with the Belt and Road Initiative. Georgia's location between Europe and Asia increased its value as a transit corridor. The China-Georgia Free Trade Agreement, signed in 2017, created new trade opportunities and supported export diversification. Trade turnover between Georgia and China doubled between 2013 and 2020, showing the growing importance of this partnership for market expansion and external economic connectivity. The comparison of EU and China influence shows that their roles were different but mainly complementary. The EU contributed more to institutional reform and regulatory stability, while China contributed more to trade growth, infrastructure links, and market integration. Therefore, Georgia's liberalization can be understood as a dual process supported by two different external actors. This hybrid model helped Georgia strengthen both its internal reform framework and its external economic opportunities.

Conclusion

This article examined Georgia's economic liberalization from 1991 to 2020 through the roles of the European Union and China. It found that the two actors influenced Georgia through different mechanisms. The EU contributed mainly to

institutional reform, legal harmonization, governance improvement, and regulatory modernization. China contributed mainly to trade expansion, infrastructure connectivity, and market diversification. The main conclusion is that these influences were mostly complementary rather than competitive. The EU strengthened the institutional basis of the Georgian economy, while China widened its market opportunities and trade connections. Together, these two directions supported Georgia's integration into the global economy and helped shape a hybrid model of liberalization. The Georgian case suggests that small transitional economies may benefit from diversified external engagement if such engagement is managed carefully. For the future, Georgia should continue balancing EU regulatory alignment with Chinese economic cooperation. It should also strengthen transparency, improve investment monitoring, support innovation, and invest in human capital to ensure more sustainable long-term development.

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